

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

CO-PRECIPIATION OF MANGANESE(II) AND ZINC CATIONS FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS BY THE DIPHOSPHATE ION

Antraptseva N.,

*National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv,
Doctor of Chemical Sciences, Professor*

Bila G.,

*National University of Food Technologies, Kyiv, Ukraine,
Candidate of Chemical Science, Docent*

Melnyk N.,

*National University of Food Technologies, Kyiv, Ukraine,
Candidate of Technical Science, Docent*

Tkachuk Y.

National University of Food Technologies, Kyiv, Ukraine, Lecturer

ABSTRACT

The conditions for co-precipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} cations from aqueous sulfate solutions with the diphosphate ion have been determined. Studies of the solid phase and mother solutions confirmed the formation of diphosphates with the composition $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ ($0 < x < 2.00$). It has been determined that they are chemically a continuous solid solution of substitution. The manganese(II) and zinc content can be controlled over a wide range, wt.%: Mn^{2+} 2.04–26.74, Zn^{2+} 2.96–30.55. Crystallographic and IR-spectroscopic characteristics were obtained for diphosphates of various compositions, confirming the state of water molecules and the distorted diphosphate anion (the P – O – P bridging angle less than 180°) in their crystal structure.

Keywords: precipitation, divalent, diphosphates, solid solution, composition, conditions.

Introduction

Individual manganese(II) and zinc diphosphates are used as a basis for the development of various inorganic materials, including active catalysts for organic synthesis, corrosion inhibitors, ceramics, and lubricating materials [1, 2].

The use of diphosphates containing both manganese(II) and zinc, with a tunable composition, makes it possible to create materials with a predictable set of improved technically valuable properties.

From a chemical standpoint, inorganic compounds containing two different cations can be obtained either as solid solutions – compounds of a single structure but with variable cation composition – or as double salts – compounds with a fixed composition.

At present, accurate prediction of the formation of double salts or solid solutions of hydrated diphosphates remains quite challenging. Assessing the possibility of formation and the homogeneity ranges of hydrated solid solutions and double phosphates requires the analysis of multiple factors. According to [3], these factors can be divided into two main groups: thermodynamic parameters (temperature, pressure, concentration, volume) and crystallochemical parameters (ionic size, structural similarity factor, nature of the chemical bond in individual phosphates). Many factors are interrelated (for example, the ionic radius depends on coordination number, valence, and temperature), while the influence of others is difficult to quantify (e.g., crystal structure type, nature of chemical bonding). To date, empirical dependencies allowing the calculation of substitution limits based on the combination of different factors have not been obtained even for the most studied salts with ionic bonds. Only empirical rules describing the effect of individual parameters under constant conditions of all others exist.

Therefore, reliable experimental data are required to predict the chemical nature of diphosphates formed during co-precipitation from aqueous solutions of divalent metal cations, particularly manganese(II) and zinc, with the diphosphate ion.

Several main methods are used to obtain individual diphosphates of divalent metals. One of them involves the reaction of the corresponding metal oxide with phosphoric acid [2, 4]. For example, $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 3H_2O$ was obtained in this way [4]. According to [2, 4, 5], hydrated diphosphates can also be obtained as intermediate products during the dehydration of more hydrated diphosphates. This method has been used to synthesize $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 2.3H_2O$ and $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot H_2O$ through thermal treatment of $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ [4].

A promising and most rational method for synthesizing hydrated diphosphates is their precipitation from aqueous solutions of salts (sulfates, chlorides, nitrates) using a solution of potassium (sodium or ammonium) diphosphate [1–3, 6]. Using this method, individual hydrated manganese(II) and zinc diphosphates were obtained by studying the interactions in the $MnCl_2 - K_4P_2O_7 - H_2O$ [6] and $ZnSO_4 - K_4P_2O_7 - H_2O$ [7] systems. This process has also been described in [8, 9]. However, most studies focused on the conditions for the formation of double salts – diphosphates of alkali and polyvalent metals.

Research specifically devoted to the conditions for obtaining hydrated diphosphates of divalent metals by co-precipitation from aqueous solutions of two divalent cations is rather scarce [3].

For example, during crystallization in the $ZnSO_4 - CoSO_4 - K_4P_2O_7 - H_2O$ system, two different limited solid solutions with distinct crystal structures and compositions are formed depending on the conditions: Zn_2 .

$x\text{Co}_x\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 0.69$) and $\text{Co}_{2-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 0.39$) [6].

For the practical synthesis of hydrated manganese(II)–zinc diphosphates as solid solutions of a specified composition, knowledge of the correlations between precipitation conditions, composition, and properties is necessary. Such data are insufficient in the literature.

The aim of this work is to study the co-precipitation of manganese(II) and zinc cations from aqueous solutions with the diphosphate ion, with particular attention to the composition and chemical nature of the resulting products.

Experimental Procedure

Aqueous solutions of $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ of “c.p.” grade were used as starting reagents. The co-precipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} cations with the diphosphate ion ($\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}$) was studied using the residual concentration method. The ratio precipitated cations ($K = \text{Mn}^{2+}/\text{Zn}^{2+}$) was varied over a wide range, keeping their total concentration constant. The ratio of cations to the precipitant ($n = \text{P}/(\sum \text{Mn}^{2+}, \text{Zn}^{2+})$) was maintained fixed.

To determine the conditions ensuring the co-precipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , separate series of experiments were conducted to specify the precipitation conditions of individual $\text{Mn}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Zn}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ diphosphates.

Based on the obtained results, the following conditions were chosen for the co-precipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} : ratio in the starting solutions ($n = \text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}/\sum \text{Mn}^{2+}, \text{Zn}^{2+} = 0.2$, $K = \text{Mn}^{2+}/\text{Zn}^{2+}$ varied within $0.05 \leq K \leq 19.00$), initial concentration of the starting solutions – 0.1 mol/l, contact time of the solid phase with the mother solution – until equilibrium, temperature range of interaction – 293–298 K.

According to the procedure, a mixture of aqueous solutions of manganese(II) and zinc sulfates in the desired ratio, and a solution of potassium diphosphate were simultaneously added to the reaction vessel under continuous stirring. The resulting solid phase was maintained in contact with the mother solution, periodically stirred, until equilibrium was reached. The precipitate was separated, washed with cooled water until no sulfate ions were detected, and recrystallized.

The total phosphorus content in the solid phase and mother solutions was determined using the quinoline-molybdate method (accuracy 0.2 rel.%), while Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} contents were determined complexometrically according to [10]. Water content in the solid phase was determined by mass loss upon heating to 1073 K (accuracy 1.0 rel.%), and anionic composition was analyzed using ion-exchange chromatography, as described in [6].

For the identification of diphosphates, a combination of physicochemical methods was used: X-ray phase analysis (Dron-4-M diffractometer, $\text{Cu K}\alpha$, internal standard NaCl), vibrational spectroscopy (infrared spectroscopy – Nexus-470 spectrometer, 400–4000 cm^{-1} , pellet pressing in KBr matrix at 0.05 rel.% sample), and Raman spectroscopy (DFS-52 spectrometer, 200–1700 cm^{-1}). Luminescence spectra were obtained using a DFS-12 spectrometer (excitation sources: xenon lamp DksEL-1000, ILGI-501 and LGN-503 lasers, helium-neon laser, spectral range 350–850 nm, temperatures 4.2, 77 and 300 K).

Results and their discussion

The results of potentiometric studies of the mother solutions, carried out to determine the time required to reach equilibrium between the solid phase and the mother solution during the co-precipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} cations with the $\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}$ ion, are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Changes in the pH of mother solutions during co-precipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} cations with the $\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}$ ion: in the absence of zinc (1), at K values ($K = \text{Mn}^{2+}/\text{Zn}^{2+}$) of 5.67 (2), 1.86 (3), 1.00 (4), 0.54 (5), 0.18 (6), and in the absence of manganese (7).

According to the presented results, the pH curves of the mother solutions obtained for different compositions of the starting solutions within the range $0.05 \leq K \leq 19.0$ are very similar in nature. The initial pH values of all curves increase during the first 3–4 days of contact and then gradually stabilize. By the seventh day, the pH values remain practically constant, indicating that equilibrium in the system is reached for all K values. Regarding the absolute pH values of the mother solutions, they increase with the Mn^{2+} content in the starting solutions, fully consistent with the stability constants of the hydroxo-complexes [10] formed during the interaction of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with water.

Chemical analysis of the mother solutions for cation contents, $C^{res.}(Mn^{2+})$, $C^{res.}(Zn^{2+})$ and phosphorus

$C^{res.}(P_2O_7^{4-})$, performed to obtain data on the precipitation behavior of the cations and the phase composition of the precipitates, showed that the residual concentrations of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} depend on the composition of the starting reagents: as the Mn^{2+} concentration increases in the initial solutions, $C^{res.}(Mn^{2+})$ rises, while $C^{res.}(Zn^{2+})$ decreases (Fig. 2). The residual $P_2O_7^{4-}$ concentration slightly decreases as well (from $4.96 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/l in the mother solution in the absence of Mn^{2+} to $3.04 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/l in the solution without Zn^{2+}). The curves representing the changes in residual concentrations of all ions are linear and show no inflections. This indicates a stable phase composition of the precipitate and the uniformity of the processes occurring during co-precipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} across all K values in the range $0.05 \leq K \leq 19.0$.

Fig. 2. Residual concentrations in the mother solutions: 1 – $C^{res.}(Mn^{2+})$, 2 – $C^{res.}(Zn^{2+})$, 3 – $C^{res.}(P_2O_7^{4-})$, 4 – pH.

The data from the chemical analysis of the mother liquors are in good agreement with the results of solid-phase analysis. (Table 1). The atomic ratio in the solid phase, $n_I = P/\Sigma M^{II}$ (Mn, Zn), which characterizes the phase composition, remains practically constant across

the entire range of K values and equals 1.00, corresponding to the theoretical value for diphosphates.

Table 1.

Characterization of diphosphates formed during coprecipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} diphosphate ions ($n = P_2O_7^{4-} / \Sigma Mn^{2+}, Zn^{2+} = 0.2; C^0 = 0.1 \text{ mol/l}$)

Ratio $K = Mn^{2+}/Zn^{2+}$	The composition of the solid phase, wt. %.				Chemical composition	Phase composition (based on X-ray diffraction and IR spectroscopy)
	Mn	Zn	P	H ₂ O		
-	29.54	-	16.52	24.23	$Mn_{2.00}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	$Mn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$
19.0	26.74	2.96	16.48	23.96	$Mn_{1.83}Zn_{0.17}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	Solid solution of the general formula $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ ($0 < x < 2.00$)
5.67	23.78	6.24	16.34	23.93	$Mn_{1.64}Zn_{0.36}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	
1.86	17.23	13.69	16.15	23.81	$Mn_{1.20}Zn_{0.80}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	
1.00	13.65	17.58	16.02	23.60	$Mn_{0.96}Zn_{1.04}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	
0.54	10.42	21.25	15.92	23.30	$Mn_{0.74}Zn_{1.26}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	
0.18	4.90	27.41	15.68	23.11	$Mn_{0.35}Zn_{1.65}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	
0.05	2.04	30.55	15.68	22.89	$Mn_{0.15}Zn_{1.85}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	$Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$
-	-	32.93	15.70	22.85	$Zn_{2.00}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	

This conclusion is supported by the results of quantitative paper chromatography, which show that the anionic composition of the solid phase, for all K values, is represented by the diphosphate anion at 98.4–97.2 rel. %.

The contents of Mn, P, and H₂O in the diphosphate formed in the absence of zinc in the starting solutions correspond to their calculated values in $Mn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$. In the absence of manganese in the starting solutions, the precipitate is a diphosphate whose chemical composition corresponds to $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$. Diphosphates obtained within the range $0.05 \leq K \leq 19.0$ contain both manganese (from 26.74 to 2.04 wt. %) and zinc (from 2.96 to 30.55 wt. %), whose contents vary systematically according to the composition of the initial solutions.

According to X-ray diffraction studies, the obtained diphosphates are represented by a crystalline phase with a structure similar to that of individual $Mn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ and $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$, the diffraction patterns of which are identical [11]. In the X-ray patterns of diphosphates containing both manganese and zinc, an increase in zinc content leads to a shift of interplanar distances toward smaller values, consistent with the

ionic radii of Mn^{2+} ($R_{ion} = 0.097 \text{ nm}$) and Zn^{2+} ($R_{ion} = 0.089 \text{ nm}$).

The interpretation of the chemical and X-ray phase analysis results allows us to conclude that a solid solution of hydrated manganese(II) and zinc diphosphates of the general formula $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ is formed. The values of x determined from chemical analysis vary from 0 to 2.0. Diphosphates of the solid solution crystallize, as indicated by the X-ray patterns, in the orthorhombic system. The unit cell parameters decrease with increasing substitution degree (x) of Mn^{2+} by Zn^{2+} (Table 2), in full agreement with Vegard's law and Retgers' rule. This provides unambiguous evidence for the formation of a solid solution of hydrated diphosphates $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ ($0 \leq x \leq 2.00$) with a wide homogeneity range.

This conclusion correlates with the results of IR spectroscopic studies of the synthesized $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ diphosphates ($0 < x < 2.00$). The structural identity is highlighted by the shapes of the spectral curves, which are generally identical for diphosphates with different degrees of substitution and similar to the spectra of individual $Mn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ and $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ diphosphates (Fig. 3).

Table 2.

Unit cell parameters of $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ diphosphates, $0 \leq x \leq 2.00$, orthorhombic system

Diphosphates	$a, \text{ \AA}$	$b, \text{ \AA}$	$c, \text{ \AA}$	$V, \text{ \AA}^3$
$Mn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	25.879 (4)	9.308 (4)	8.481 (3)	2043.8 (9)
$Mn_{1.64}Zn_{0.36}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	25.864 (7)	9.292 (3)	8.469 (2)	2035.0 (9)
$Mn_{1.20}Zn_{0.80}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	25.751 (6)	9.247 (2)	8.441 (2)	2009.9 (8)
$Mn_{0.96}Zn_{1.04}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	25.693 (6)	9.229 (2)	8.425 (2)	1997.7 (8)
$Mn_{0.74}Zn_{1.26}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	25.669 (4)	9.206 (1)	8.412 (1)	1987.9 (5)
$Mn_{0.35}Zn_{1.65}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	25.616 (2)	9.182 (1)	8.392 (1)	1973.8 (3)
$Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$	25.581 (2)	9.164 (1)	8.368 (1)	1961.4 (3)

Fig. 3. IR absorption spectra of $Mn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ (1), solid solutions $Mn_{1.64}Zn_{0.36}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ (2), $Mn_{0.96}Zn_{1.04}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ (3), $Mn_{0.35}Zn_{1.65}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ (4) and $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ (5)

Analysis of the IR spectra $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ ($0 \leq x \leq 2.00$) diphosphates, performed to evaluate the energetic state of water molecules and the diphosphate anion in their crystal structures, revealed absorption bands characteristic of water molecule vibrations ($3600\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1650\text{--}1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$), the $P_2O_7^{4-}$ anionic sublattice ($1150\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and M–O bonds ($500\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

In the region of O–H stretching vibrations of water molecules, a broad absorption band is observed, with the number of maxima decreasing from four for $Mn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ and $Mn_{1.64}Zn_{0.36}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ to two broad maxima for $Mn_{0.96}Zn_{1.04}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$, $Mn_{0.35}Zn_{1.65}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ and $Zn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ (Fig. 3). In the frequency range of bending vibrations of water molecules ($1650\text{--}1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$), the IR spectra of $Mn_2P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ and $Mn_{1.64}Zn_{0.36}P_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ show a relatively narrow absorption band with two maxima and a shoulder on the low-frequency side. Its intensity decreases with decreasing manganese (II) content in the diphosphate structure and is practically absent in diphosphates with $x \geq 1.65$.

The IR spectra of $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ diphosphates in the anionic skeletal vibration region ($1150\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$) consist of 12 distinct absorption bands of varying intensity. These correspond, in terms of group frequencies, to the stretching (ν_s and ν_{as}) vibrations of the

PO_3 groups of the diphosphate anion, bending vibrations of the P–O groups, and stretching (ν_s and ν_{as}) vibrations of the P–O–P groups [12].

Interpretation of IR spectroscopic data of $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ in the region of vibrations of water molecules indicates the presence in their structure of three crystallographically non-identical types of water molecules that are part of the coordination environment of the cation. This is evidenced by the three components of the water bending vibration band, which allow a fairly reliable assessment of how water molecules are integrated into the crystal hydrate structure. The energetic states of two types of water molecules, judging by the $\delta(H_2O)$ peak positions, are similar, so their corresponding absorption bands may partially overlap, whereas the third type differs, as observed in the IR spectra of the diphosphates (Fig. 3).

Analysis of the spectral positions and shapes of the $\nu(OH)$ absorption bands in the IR spectra of $Mn_{2-x}Zn_xP_2O_7 \cdot 5H_2O$ (broadened and shifted to lower frequencies compared to the vibrations of free water, $\nu_0 = 3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicates that water molecules are strongly bound both through oxygen and hydrogen atoms. The presence of a rigid hydrogen-bonding network in the diphosphate structure is also evidenced by the increased frequencies of bending vibrations ($1658\text{--}1628\text{ cm}^{-1}$) compared to the bending vibration frequency of

a free water molecule (1595 cm^{-1} [11]). The simultaneous presence of high- and low-frequency $\nu(\text{OH})$ maxima in the IR spectra of the diphosphates indicates varying degrees of involvement of each water molecule in hydrogen bonding of different strength and directionality. Some OH groups (absorption maxima at $3300\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) participate in relatively strong hydrogen bonds ($32\text{--}36\text{ kJ/mol}$), likely with the diphosphate anion ($\text{M}^{2+}\text{--OH}_2\text{...OP}_2\text{O}_6^{4-}$). While other OH-groups (absorption bands around 3500 cm^{-1}) are involved in weaker hydrogen bonds ($9\text{--}22\text{ kJ/mol}$) with OH-groups of other water molecules ($\text{M}^{2+}\text{--OH}_2\text{--OH}_2$). The frequency difference of $\nu(\text{OH})$ in the IR spectra of diphosphates of different compositions is significant: for $\text{Mn}_{1.64}\text{Zn}_{0.36}\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ it reaches 340 cm^{-1} and decreases to 160 cm^{-1} for $\text{Mn}_{0.35}\text{Zn}_{1.65}\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. These values are much higher than those for a symmetrically loaded water molecule (110 cm^{-1} [12]), indicating that water molecules in the $\text{Mn}_{2-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ structure are asymmetric. Moreover, the non-equivalence of individual OH-bonds decreases with increasing zinc content in the diphosphate.

Analysis of the spectral data in the anionic skeletal vibration region ($1150\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$) shows that in the range of PO_3 stretching vibrations ($1200\text{--}990\text{ cm}^{-1}$) four absorption bands and two shoulders are observed. In the frequency range characteristic of asymmetric $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{POP})$ vibrations of the P–O–P bridging bond ($950\text{--}890\text{ cm}^{-1}$), a strong doublet absorption band is present, while in the symmetric $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{POP})$ stretching region ($750\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) there is a single band. This set of absorption bands indicates a low symmetry of the $\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}$ anion, characteristic of a bent P–O–P bridging configuration [12]. The presence of the $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{POP})$ band in the IR spectra of the synthesized diphosphates can be interpreted as the absence of alternative constraints, unequivocally indicating a non-centrosymmetric C_{2v} anion configuration (P–O–P angle less than 180°); for a centrosymmetric D_{3d} $\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ group, only $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{POP})$ is allowed (P–O–P angle = 180°).

The position of the $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{POP})$ frequency in the IR spectra of the diphosphates changes depending on the composition of the solid solution: as the zinc content increases, the $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{POP})$ maximum shifts to higher frequencies (Fig. 3). This may indicate a decrease in the P–O–P bridging angle. However, since the position of the $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{POP})$ maximum is also influenced by the increase in the dynamic coupling constant of the P–O(P) bond, which changes for the same reasons, an additional criterion was used to assess the deformation of the P–O–P angle, namely the parameter $\Delta = [\nu_{\text{as}} - \nu_{\text{s}}(\text{POP})] / [\nu_{\text{as}} + \nu_{\text{s}}(\text{POP})]$. Calculations of Δ for diphosphates with compositions $\text{Mn}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mn}_{1.20}\text{Zn}_{0.80}\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mn}_{0.96}\text{Zn}_{1.04}\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mn}_{0.74}\text{Zn}_{1.26}\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Zn}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ showed a gradual decrease in Δ values from 13.00, 12.33, 12.30, 11.99 to 11.45 %, respectively. This indicates a gradual reduction of the P–O–P angle with increasing zinc content in the diphosphate.

Thus, by co-precipitation from aqueous solutions of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} sulfates with the diphosphate anion, hydrated diphosphates of the general formula $\text{Mn}_{2-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were obtained. By chemical nature,

they are a solid substitution solution, the region of homogeneity (x) of which is $0 < x < 2.00$.

IR spectroscopy allowed determination of the state of the crystalhydrate water molecules and the diphosphate anion in the crystal structure of the diphosphates. It was shown that asymmetric water molecules and the deformed diphosphate anion (with a P–O–P bridging angle less than 180°) are part of the cation coordination polyhedron. Water molecules participate in the realization of H-bonds of different strength and direction.

Conclusions

The conditions for the co-precipitation of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} cations from aqueous sulfate solutions by diphosphate ion were determined: ratio in the composition of the initial solutions ($n = \text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-} / \sum \text{Mn}^{2+}, \text{Zn}^{2+} = 0.2$, $K = \text{Mn}^{2+} / \text{Zn}^{2+}$ within $0.05 \leq K \leq 19.00$), initial concentration of the solutions – 0.1 mol/l , contact time of the solid phase with the mother liquor – until equilibrium is reached, temperature range – $293\text{--}298\text{ K}$.

Studies of the solid phase and mother solutions confirmed the formation, under the specified conditions, of hydrated diphosphates with the general formula $\text{Mn}_{2-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($0 < x < 2.00$). It was established that chemically they represent a continuous substitution solid solution. The content of manganese(II) and zinc can be controllably varied over a wide range, wt. %: Mn^{2+} 2.04–26.74, Zn^{2+} 2.96–30.55.

Crystallographic and IR spectroscopic characteristics were obtained for diphosphates of various compositions, confirming the state of water molecules and the deformed diphosphate anion (with a P–O–P bridging angle less than 180°) in their crystal structure.

References

1. Acton A.Q. Phosphates – advances in research and application. – Atlanta, Georgia: Scholarly Editions, 2013. – 374 p.
2. Shchegrov L. Phosphates of divalent metals. – K.: Nauk. dumka, 1987. – 216 p.
3. Anraptseva N.M., Solod N.V. Solid solutions and double phosphates of bivalent metals. – K: Center of polygraphy KOMPRINT, 2018. – 342 p.
4. Konstant Z.A., Dindune A.P. Phosphates of divalent metals. – Riga: Zinatne, 1997. – 371 p.
5. Kanazawa T. Inorganic Phosphate Materials. Elsevier, New York, 1989. – 297 p.
6. Anraptseva N.M., Solod N.V., Kravchenko O.O. Crystallization features of solid solutions of hydrated diphosphates in the system $\text{ZnSO}_4\text{--CoSO}_4\text{--K}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7\text{--H}_2\text{O}$ // Functional Materials, 2024, 31(3). – P.396–404.
7. Anraptseva N.M., Solod N.V., Kochkodan O.D., Kravchenko O.O. Co-precipitation of cations of zinc and divalent metals out of phosphoric acid solutions // Functional materials, 2022. Vol. 29, No 4. P. 597–604.
8. Song Z. Wang J. Syntheses, structures and characterization of non-centrosymmetric $\text{Rb}_2\text{Zn}_3(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2$ and centrosymmetric $\text{Cs}_2\text{M}_3(\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2$ ($\text{M} = \text{Zn}$ and Mg) // Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers, 2020. Vol. 7, No 18. P. 3482 – 3490.

9. Elhafiane F.Z., Khaoulaf R., Harcharras M., Brouzi K. Synthesis, crystal structure, vibrational spectroscopy and electrochemical investigations of a new acidic metal pyrophosphate $\text{NiK}_{1.18}\text{N}_{0.82}(\text{H}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ // *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 2021, 1245, 131234.

10. Scoog D.A., West D.M., Holler F.J. *Fundamentals of Analytical Chemistry*. – Boston: Sanders college publ., 1992. – 378 p.

11. Powder Diffraction File. JCPDS. Published by International Centre for Diffraction Data. Swarthmore, USA. – 1986. к. 07–0087.

12. Nakamoto K. *Infrared and Raman spectra of inorganic and coordination compounds. Part B. Applications in coordination, organometallic and bioinorganic chemistry*. – John Wiley & Sons. Inc., 2009. – 424 p.